

CTH3 (Bili Mukthi), a white-grained, cold- and blast (BI)-tolerant rice for southern Karnataka, India

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About 0.3 million ha of rice is cultivated in southern Karnataka under both canal- and reservoir-irrigated conditions. Canal-irrigated rice is planted during Jun-Jul because of the assured, regulated release of stored water. But reservoir-fed rice can be planted only after the reservoirs are full. This delay normally leads to late planting — sometimes not until September.

Even the very early-maturing recommended varieties, when planted after mid-August, flower during November (winter) and do not perform well. For such conditions, the only suitable variety that has been recently released is Mukthi (CTH1), a red-grained rice that few farmers prefer.

CTH3, a new selection from the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery planted at Bangalore during 1983 winter, was multiplied for seed during 1984 and tested in three locations within Karnataka. It can meet the demand for a white-grained, cold- and BI-tolerant variety, and can supplement Mukthi over large areas in the reservoir-irrigated winter rice belt.

CTH3 was obtained from IR9202-25-1-3, derived from TR2053-521-1-1/K116/KN-1B-361-1-8-6-9-1. The selection is 95 cm high, has medium bold grains, moderate tillering, and grows normally from germination to maturity in any season because of its cold and BI tolerance and photoperiod insensitivity.

It yielded OS-5.0 t grain/ha during normal season and 0.6 to 1.9 t grain/ha during winter compared with 0.02-1.1 t/ha for best checks Mangala and CH2 (both white-grained) under winter conditions.

The table summarizes the performance of CTH3 for 6 yr at Bangalore. Its leaf BI score of 2 and 2% neck BI are better than the 7 and 5% for susceptible variety Halubblu. The performance of CTH3 at

Performance of cold-tolerant varieties from 2 plantings (Sep, Oct) at Bangalore, India, 1985-86 to 1990-91.

Entry	Grain yield (t/ha)												Total mean (t/ha)	Increase (%)over CH2	Blast			
	1985-86		1986-87		1987-88	1988-89		1989-90		1990-91		Mean			Sep	Oct	Leaf ^a	Neck (%)
	Sep	Oct	Sep	Oct	Sep	Sep	Oct	Sep	Oct	Sep	Oct							
CTH1	2.3	1.7	4.9	3.5	3.9	1.3	1.5	1.4	2.0	1.4	2.6	2.0	2.3	107	2	0		
CTH3	1.2	0.6	5.0	1.9	1.8	0.5	0.9	1.8	1.0	0.7	1.9	1.0	1.5	28	2	2		
Checks																		
Mangala	0.3	0.1	3.6	0.7	1.4	0.5	0.0	1.1	1.1	0.6	1.3	0.4	0.8	—	2	2.4		
CH2	1.3	1.1	3.6	0.5	2.2	0.4	—	1.0	0.7	0.6	1.5	0.7	1.1		2	1.5		
LSD	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.1	ns	0.3	0.2	0.3	0.2	—	—	—					
CV (%)	14.9	16.1	13.7	14.2	19.2	—	27.5	21.4	23.5	19.4	—	—	—					

^aScored using Standard evaluation system for rice (0-9).

Bangalore, Mandya, and Mudigere during 1985-91 and on private farms in Mysore district has confirmed its superiority in winter and high degree of BI tolerance.

It is now approved for farm trials in Karnataka in the hill zone and is spreading from farmer to farmer in Mysore district under the name Bili Mukthi. □

Integrated germplasm improvement—rainfed

TKM10, a new higher yielding rice for semidry conditions

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Rice is cultivated on about 45,000 ha under semidry conditions (rainfed lowland-subsequently irrigated) in Chengalpattu MGR district of Tamil Nadu, India.

Table 1. Overall yield performance of TKM10.

Trial	no.	Yield (t/ha)	
		TKM10	TKM1
Research Station			
Tirur	4	1.9	1.1
Adaptive research trial			
October 1989-90	28	2.0	1.7
Adaptive research trial			
October 1990-91	19	3.8	2.7
Mean		2.6	1.8

Table 2. Drought score at RSS, Tirur, Tamil Nadu, 1989-91.

Entry	Parentage	1989-90		1990-91	
		Tolerance	Recovery	Tolerance	Recovery
TKM 10	CO 31/C22	1	1	1	1
IR20	IR262/TKM6	5	5	3	5
TKM1	Pisini (local selection)	1	1	1	1
CO 31	GEB24/ <i>O. perennis</i>	1	1	1	1
IET 1444	TN1/CO 29	5	3	5	3
TKMY	TKM7/IR8	3	3	3	1

^aScored using SES.

TKM1, a local genotype released 30 yr ago as a pureline variety from Pisini, was previously the only suitable variety for this environment.

We initiated breeding work to develop a drought-tolerant, high-yielding semidry rice. This work resulted in the identification of elite culture TM8602, a hybrid derivative of the cross CO 31/C22, which was released as TKM 10. This culture is a semitall plant with nonlodging culms.

Trials conducted in both RRS and farmers' fields revealed the high-yielding potential of this genotype compared with check TKM1. TKM10 averaged 2.6 t grain/ha (Table 1) with a maximum yield of 5.2 t/ha recorded in a trial plot that received enough rainfall during sowing and vegetative and reproductive phases.

TKM10 matures in 135 d under direct seeding. Its seedlings, along with checks, were assessed for drought tolerance during the vegetative phase in 1989-90 and 1990-